

Deliverable D3.1

Guidance on microbiome sample accessioning

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Work package Leader	<i>EMBL</i>
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Lead contributor to Deliverable	<i>EMBL</i>
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1. Background

Microbiomes comprise communities of microorganisms (i.e., microbiota that includes bacteria, archaea, protists, fungi and microalgae) and their "theatre of activity" (i.e., structural elements, metabolites, signal molecules, mobile genetic elements, as well as surrounding environmental conditions). Microbiomes play a key role in maintaining life on Earth by providing a range of essential ecosystem services and are indispensable for the health of plants, animals and humans. Thus, there is a wide consensus that by harnessing microbiome functions society would be better placed to tackle global challenges such as food security, health and wellbeing, food waste management, and climate change mitigation. To facilitate the science necessary to achieve key advances in microbiome research, methodologies and technologies to capture or create, ensure stable long-term maintenance, and experimentally perturb microbiomes are required. Research infrastructures currently lack optimised methodologies and technologies to preserve and provide access to microbiome samples and massive amounts of associated data. MICROBE is designed to address these issues by building upon and connecting: (1) technical solutions for microbiome preservation, propagation and functionality assessment, (2) novel ecological concepts (i.e. "core microbiome" and "microbial keystone taxa"), and (3) data infrastructures.

In light of the vast diversity and complexity of microbiomes, MICROBE will employ a focused approach that will ensure that the required developments and assessments can be comprehensively executed, resulting in a robust set of solutions. For this, a representative set of microbiome samples from soil, seed, marine and human systems has been selected. This set also has existing data sets and knowledge available and is linked to ongoing research projects, ensuring easy accessibility of samples and data, and also access to external partners for the validation of methods developed during the project.

MICROBE Work Package 3 (WP3) is dedicated to the delivery of a comprehensive data infrastructure for microbiome biobanking. Such a data infrastructure requires a robust technical platform; data standardisation measures; support for cross-linkage between microbiome sample records and their derivatives, and support for cross-linkage between sample records and any data that characterises those samples; and a strong capability for handling and managing data in accordance with the FAIR principles¹ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)

Operational Framework for Microbiome Biobanking:

Technical Platform: Maintaining systems for efficiently managing and storing data related to microbiome samples, analytical data, and derived resources.

Data Standardisation Measures: Enforcing standardised procedures for the submission, storage and analysis of the data and metadata derived from microbiome samples. This guarantees consistency across various research endeavours and facilitates meaningful comparisons between studies.

Linkages Between Biological Samples, Analytical Data, and Derived Resources: Ensuring clear connections between the biological samples (e.g., soil, seed, human gut, marine microbiomes), the analytical data generated from these samples, and the resources derived from them (such as isolates). This linkage is important for traceability and reproducibility. Handling human derived samples has data privacy and GDPR considerations; a discussion of these issues is out of scope for this deliverable. We expect to address any data privacy issues as we progress through the MICROBE project and will provide a detailed report on how MICROBE's data infrastructure handles GDPR in D3.4 (M36).

Handling and Managing FAIR data: To be a trusted research infrastructure requires that the data derived from research outputs is FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Early steps on any journey towards ensuring data is FAIR tend to start with making those data readily discoverable and, where possible, retrievable using a standard identifier. Sharing records in established public repositories is a good way to accomplish this aim.

This document illustrates the role of the BioSamples² database in providing microbiome sample accession numbers. Through BioSamples, MICROBE gains access to a global infrastructure for sample metadata identification and retrieval through standard accessions and standard formats. We expect BioSamples, along with the European Nucleotide Archive³ (ENA) and MGnify⁴, to make up the key components of the MICROBE data infrastructure.

2. Introduction

The BioSamples database (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/>), an ELIXIR Core Deposition Database⁵, stores and supplies descriptions and metadata about biological samples used in research and development by academia and industry. Samples are either 'reference' samples (e.g. from 1000 Genomes, HipSci, FAANG) or experimental samples, and have been used in an assay that has generated publicly available data. BioSamples supports links between sample records and any sample derived datasets, including sequence based datasets such as those held in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) or ArrayExpress⁶, -omics based datasets such as those

in PRIDE⁷ or MetaboLights⁸, and any other assay based databases. It provides links to assays and specific samples and accepts direct submissions of sample information.

This document describes the role of BioSamples in providing sample accessions within the MICROBE project, particularly in the context of microbiome biobanking research. BioSamples will be utilised for the submission, cross-linking, and tracking of samples and sample collections. To successfully fulfil this role, our objectives are to support registering samples in BioSamples, compiling unique sample identifiers (accession numbers), and linking sample records and associated sequencing data to the taxonomic and functional identification of metagenomes.

Our focus is on ensuring traceability and connectivity between samples, to enable the data to be FAIR and sustainable beyond the life of the project. MICROBE aims to enable the establishment of microbiome biobanking research infrastructures in future. The guidance provided by MICROBE, and the examples that will be generated within the MICROBE project, can be replicated by others once the project ends. Specifically, this document serves as a functional and technical guide for BioSamples sample registration and submission. It will cover various options for registering and submitting samples, considering the different stages of sample processing. The goal is to support downstream assessment and validation analysis by establishing clear links between synthetic consortia and their original samples.

3. MICROBE data summary

Table 1 provides an overview of the data types that will be generated and collected by the MICROBE project, as well as a summary of plans for hosting solutions, mechanisms of data sharing, and the project partners who will generate and curate those data types according to the principles laid out in Deliverable 7.1 Data Management Plan (DMP) to ensure data interoperability.

Table 1. Overview of data types that will be generated by the MICROBE project, their proposed hosting solutions, and the partners responsible for ensuring data interoperability.

Type of data	Proposed hosting solution	Data sharing mechanism	Data generators and curators
Microbiome and microbial genome sequence data	European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) at EMBL-EBI	Open access (after publication)	CABI, INRAE, DSMZ, HMGU, EMBL, AIT, SU
Microbiome and microbial transcriptome sequence data	European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) at EMBL-EBI	Open access (after publication)	SU
Microbiome and microbial sample descriptions	BioSamples database at EMBL-EBI	Open access	CABI, INRAE, DSMZ, HMGU, EMBL, AIT, SU
Functional and taxonomic microbiome profiles	MGnify and ENA databases at EMBL-EBI	Open access (after publication)	EMBL, DSMZ, INRAE, AIT, CABI, MUG, HMGU, SU
Metabarcoding sequence data and metagenome-assembled genomes	ENA database at EMBL-EBI	Open access (after publication)	EMBL, DSMZ, HMGU, AIT

Along with newly generated data, MICROBE will make considerable use of existing publicly available microbiome datasets of the type outlined in Table 1. We will draw data from existing hosting solutions.

This document further details microbiome and microbial sample registration and deposition to the BioSamples database at EMBL-EBI.

4. Sample Registration and Accessioning Overview

Sample checklists

Samples with rich metadata are important for the discovery, re-use, and interoperability of data. The use of sample checklists enable the collection and submission of standardised metadata; for a sample submission to BioSamples the checklists define a list of attributes which must be

provided, and constrain what can be provided for each attribute ensuring consistency across attribute values and enabling comparison across samples and associated data. There are a number of existing sample checklists available in BioSamples, developed both by the Genome Standards Consortium⁹ and the ENA in collaboration with different communities . A table of existing checklists available in BioSamples that may be suitable for MICROBE use cases is provided in Table 2 below.

Table 2. List of existing checklists available in BioSamples suitable for MICROBE

Human-associated	Water	Soil	Metagenomes
GSC MlXS human gut	GSC MlXS sediment	GSC MlXS soil	GSC MIMAGS
GSC MlXS human oral	GSC MlXS water		GSC MISAGS
GSC MlXS human skin	ENA Micro B3		GSC MIUVIGS
GSC MlXS human vaginal	ENA Tara Oceans		ENA binned metagenome

To register samples with BioSamples in accordance with community defined standards and assign an accession number to those samples, a submitter may need to undertake some or all of the following general steps:

1. Create a submitter account for BioSamples
2. [Authenticate](#) with BioSamples using a submitter account
3. Provision a new sample record and request an accession number
4. Provide sample metadata in a BioSamples supported [data format](#) that is valid against minimal requirements defined by a chosen community standard as in above table
5. Provide as much additional sample metadata beyond the minimal requirements as possible
6. Cross-link the sample record to other sample records to capture a [relationship](#) that reflect the provenance or lineage of the sample
7. Provide [external references](#) from BioSamples to datasets derived from them (e.g. sequence data in ENA)

Figure 1: BioSamples submission flow

** Depending on the precise sample registration option chosen (see Section 6), different combinations of these general steps may be appropriate.

5. Data format

BioSamples JSON Format (JSON)

JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) is an open standard file format and data interchange format that uses human-readable text to store and transmit data objects consisting of attribute–value pairs and arrays (or other serializable values). It is a common data format with diverse uses in electronic data interchange, including that of web applications with servers. The BioSamples database uses a standardised profile of JSON to capture sample metadata descriptions, allowing for detailed annotations, including ontology markup to be associated with sample accession numbers.

Although BioSamples JSON format is not a community standard, it is very easy to adapt and convert to other sample descriptors, and tools are available to map to similar formats (e.g. ISA-TAB¹⁰ or BioSchemas¹¹). This is a suitable format for long-term archiving.

BioSamples TSV (ISA-Tab) format

The TSV file upload data format supported by BioSamples adheres to the ISA Tab standard, and you can find the corresponding documentation at this [link](#)

6. Functional specifications for registration and deposition of samples to the BioSamples database

6.1 User accounts and authentication in BioSamples

BioSamples submitters can choose to authenticate through either the EBI Authentication, Authorization, and Profile (AAP) service or the ENA Webin Authentication Service. For MICROBE submissions, it is recommended to utilise the Webin Authentication Service. The subsequent sections of the document will provide detailed guidance.

For a quick reference on setting up a user in the Webin Authentication Service, please visit the [link](#).

6.2 Overview of Sample Registration Options

1. **Before the collection of samples:** This could involve requesting accessions to print labels on empty vials or test tubes.
2. **After sample collection and registration of sample with minimal metadata:** This might be done for LIMS integration with recording minimal metadata in BioSamples.
3. **Before the submission of assay data:** Accessions may be requested to register samples with full metadata before data deposition, facilitating linking across databases.
4. **During the submission of assay data:** Accessions may be requested while submitting data to ENA.

All BioSample services function the same way for each use case, but the choice of which service to use may vary depending on your specific scenario.

6.3 Steps involved in sample registration for each option.

Figure 2: BioSamples sample registration workflows

6.3.1 Before the collection of samples

1. Ensure authentication through the Webin Authentication Service.
2. Utilize the BioSamples V2 API to accession all estimated samples collectively. This involves generating a range of estimates for the anticipated sample quantity, particularly in cases where an exact number cannot be determined.

6.3.2 After sample collection and registration of sample with minimal metadata

If samples has been collected and they possess minimal metadata (e.g., taxon information or material type) for each sample record, consider the following steps:

1. Ensure authentication through the Webin Authentication Service.
2. Samples can be submitted with limited metadata using the BioSamples TSV file uploader. Detailed guidance on this process can be found in the file uploader guide [here](#).

6.3.3 Before the submission of assay data

1. Ensure authentication through the Webin Authentication Service.
2. Samples can be submitted with as much metadata as possible using the BioSamples TSV file uploader. Reference the file uploader guide for detailed instructions [here](#).

6.3.4 During the submission of assay data

ENA submissions seamlessly integrate with BioSamples, automatically generating BioSamples accessions and establishing corresponding sample records. If your data necessitates submission to an archive other than ENA, kindly notify us, and we will furnish the requisite guidance.

6.4 Sample Relationships in BioSamples

Sample relationships in BioSamples describe the connections between two BioSamples, falling into submission, technical, or biological categories. These relationships establish links between different samples and facilitate relationship-based graph searches.

When a submitter provides relationship information for one sample, corresponding reverse relationships in related samples are automatically generated.

BioSamples recommends three types of sample relationships:

1. Derived From:

- **Description:** Sample A is derived from Sample B.
- **Examples:**
 - Gut microbiome samples taken from a host organism
 - Isolate samples cultured from an environmental sample
 - Cell line samples created from a tissue sample.
 - Viral samples separated from saliva sample.

2. Same As:

- **Description:** Sample A is the same as Sample B. Useful for linking duplicated samples.

3. Child Of:

- **Description:** Sample A is the child of Sample B.
- **Examples:**
 - Patient A is the child of Patient B.
- Note that we do not expect “child of” to be relevant for microbiome research

These relationships provide a structured framework for understanding the connections and associations between various samples within the BioSamples database.

Examples:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/SAMEA8141702>
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/SAMEA110758231>
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/SAMEA6847992>
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/SAMEA13009075>
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/SAMEA112168801>

6.5 External References in EBI BioSamples: Connecting Samples with External Databases

Much of the initial data generation in MICROBE is sequence based. EBI BioSamples contains external references that serve as links that connect a BioSample entry to major sequence based databases such as ENA, MGnify or ArrayExpress, and we expect this to be heavily used to link MICROBE data together. BioSamples external references, however, are not limited to purely sequence-based databases and can be used to link to any relevant other external databases or resources.

External references provide a means to associate a BioSample with additional information or data available in other repositories, databases, biobanks or culture collections. External references help establish connections between BioSamples and related information, enhancing the interoperability and accessibility of data.

For example, if a BioSample corresponds to a specific organism or sample type that is well-described in an external database, the BioSample entry might include an external reference to that database. This reference allows users to access more detailed information about the sample from an external source. Culture collections commonly hold detailed information about reference strains and BioSamples external references can be used to link the experimental data in public repositories to the reference strain information held in a culture collection when shared BioSamples identifiers are used.

The use of external references in BioSamples supports the integration of data from various sources and promotes a more comprehensive understanding of the biological samples catalogued in the database. It also facilitates cross-referencing and data linking between BioSamples and other relevant repositories.

Table 3. Examples of samples in BioSamples having external references to other archives

Sample URL	Description	External Database Link
SAMN22048569	A sample having a link to a study in dbGaP	dbGaP Study Link
SAMEA4092883	A sample having a link to a cell line in hpscreg	hpscreg Cell Line Link
SAMEA6847992	A sample having a link to a dataset in EGA	EGA Dataset Link
SAMEA5643394	A sample having a link to a study in EBI BioStudies database	EBI BioStudies Link
SAMEA114478613	A sample having a link to a study in the European Variation Archive (EVA)	EVA Study Link
SAMEA5429728	Sample having 'culture collection' and 'specimen voucher' which leads to findability in another repository	US NPGS Link US NPGS Link

7. MICROBE current sample collection (a subset)

Figure 3: Illustration of MICROBE sample collection

Table 4. Contains the Illustration of the samples in BioSamples

Sample name	Sample accession (in test)	Sample link in BioSamples
Parent sample	SAMEA130812025	link
SG1	SAMEA130812026	link
SG2	SAMEA130812027	link
SG3	SAMEA130812028	link
AIT Child Sample 4	SAMEA130812029	link
AIT Child Sample 5	SAMEA130812030	link
AIT Child Sample 6	SAMEA130812031	link
DSMZ Child Sample 1	SAMEA130812487	link
DSMZ Child Sample 2	SAMEA130812490	link
DSMZ Child Sample 3	SAMEA130812491	link

** for a faceted search of all MICROBE samples [click here](#) **

8. The Vital Role of Sample Metadata and BioSamples Submission in the MICROBE Project

Introduction to Sample Metadata:

Highlighting the significance of sample details in the MICROBE project is crucial. Accurate sample metadata provide essential information about microbiome samples, ensuring that the results can be interpreted effectively.

Role of Checklists in Standardisation:

The utilisation of sample checklists is important in standardising the submission of metadata, promoting consistency across various research endeavours and enabling discovery of samples and data based on key metadata fields. A list of sample checklists is provided in Table 2 which may be suitable for use in MICROBE. It may be the case that new checklists might need to be developed where current checklists do not capture attributes important for MICROBE. Note there is no suitable Seed checklist available in BioSamples and it is very likely one will need to be developed as part of MICROBE. In deliverable 3.2 (M24, Search services for microbiome sample and dataset discovery across select core public repositories) we will report on the importance of checklists in facilitating intuitive search and discuss how we have addressed any gaps in checklist coverage.

Establishing a Foundation with BioSamples:

By documenting and submitting metadata to BioSamples, the MICROBE project establishes a foundation for a robust and searchable collection of samples within the BioSamples database. This not only facilitates internal research efforts but also lays the groundwork for the future MICROBE data portal.

Efficient Searching and Collaboration:

The deposition of sample metadata enables efficient searching of samples which includes faceted searches, helping collaboration and data exploration.

Linkage with External Resources:

Moreover, the linkage between metadata and external resources ensures access of supplementary information, enhancing traceability within the MICROBE project.

Conclusion:

In essence, the submission of samples with rich metadata to BioSamples play a key role in shaping the accessibility, usability, and interconnectedness of microbiome data in the broader scientific community.

This deliverable report highlights the importance of standardisation and linkage of samples, as well as a practical guide on how to accession samples through submission of sample records to the BioSamples database.

Ensuring sample registration in BioSamples will enable access to data from specific microbiomes to be used as reference points for research. The establishment of standards for microbiota will drive convergence within the field and ensure greater interoperability of data in future. Within the project, the generation of new datasets that are compliant with newly established standards,, will create a cohort of data that can be leveraged to begin understanding biological signals, especially when coupled with state-of-the-art analytical methodologies deployed, for example within MGnify pipelines.

9. Technical Details

9.1 Authentication in BioSamples

9.1.1 Creating a Webin Submission Account

Registration of a user account with the Webin Authentication Service can be done easily using this [link](#).

9.1.2 Getting an auth token from the Webin Authentication Service in a programmatic way

```
TOKEN=$(curl --location --request POST
'https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/auth/token' --header 'Content-Type:
application/json' --data-raw '{
  "authRealms": [
    "ENA"
  ],
  "password": "your_password",
  "username": "your_webin_id"
}')

```

9.1.3 Getting an auth token from the Webin Authentication Service using the link and constructing a payload in the below format

```
{
  "authRealms": [
    "ENA"
  ],
  "password": "your_webin_account_password",
  "username": "Webin-XXXXX_your_webin_id"
}
```

9.1.4 Logging into BioSamples using your webin account information (applicable for sample metadata submission using the file uploader)

Figure 4: BioSamples file upload submission login page

Please refer to the [cookbook section](#) for instructions on using the uploader. You can download an example upload file [here](#).

Login using AAP WEBIN

Username
Webin-XXXXX

Password
●●●●●●●●

Sign in to upload

9.2 Sample registration in BioSamples

9.2.1 Options 1 and 2

1. Before the collection of samples
2. After sample collection but before the registration of sample metadata

Use case: Accessioning of samples.

Explanation: Sample metadata is unavailable at this stage; unique accessions are generated for later use, and metadata submission.

Technical details:

BioSamples V1 API can be used to generate a single sample accession per API call.
 BioSamples V2 API can generate 'n' sample accessions per API call (The API is designed to generate 'n' accessions per API call, but it is recommended to generate accessions in splits of 1000 to avoid changes of EBI load balancer gateway timeouts.

** Overall using V2 reduces the number of API calls from n to n/1000 over V1 (considering split size = 1000)

Using V1 with WEBIN-AUTH:

```
curl 'http://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/accession' -i -X POST -H "Content-Type: application/json;charset=UTF-8" -H "Accept: application/json" -H "Authorization: Bearer $TOKEN" -d '{"name": "SAMPLE_NAME"}'
```

Using V2 with WEBIN-AUTH:

```
curl --location --request POST 'https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/v2/samples/bulk-accession' \
--header 'Authorization: Bearer TOKEN' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--data-raw '[{"name": "SAMPLE_1_NAME"}, {"name": "SAMPLE_2_NAME"}, {"name": "SAMPLE_3_NAME"}]'
```

(** replace www with wwwdev for test accessioning)

Please note:

TOKEN in the accessioning curl commands is the authentication token

Submission minimal fields: Sample name

9.2.2 Option 3

3. Before the submission of assay data

Use case: Submission of sample metadata.

Explanation: Sample metadata is available at this stage and is ready for submission to BioSamples

Recommendation: Use the BioSamples file uploader to bulk upload samples with metadata to BioSamples. Guidance to use the BioSamples file uploader is available [here](#)

9.2.3 Option 4

4. During the submission of assay data

Use case: ENA metadata and data submission.

Explanation: The assay data is ready for submission. At this stage, we recommend submitting both samples and assay data to ENA. ENA automatically forwards all samples to BioSamples, ensuring the creation of BioSamples records as well.

Recommendation: We recommend consulting the ENA submission documentation available at this [link](#) and proceeding to submit samples metadata and assay data to ENA.

10. References

¹Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016).

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⁵<https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>

⁶<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress>

⁷<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride>

⁸<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights>

⁹<https://www.gensc.org/pages/standards-intro.html>

¹⁰<https://www.nature.com/documents/scidata-isatab-specification.pdf>

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